

Design of Chatbot Web Interface for the Department of IT based on RAG Technology using LLM Models

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Abstract

This research project presents the design and evaluation of a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) chatbot developed for the Department of IT in a university. The primary objective is to automate and enhance the dissemination of academic information, addressing the shortcomings of existing static websites and email-based support systems. Traditional systems often prove inefficient as users struggle to locate relevant information, content becomes outdated, interactivity is limited, and information overload leads to user frustration and increased staff workload. To resolve these challenges, a RAG-based chatbot was developed by integrating two state-of-the-art Large Language Models (LLMs): GPT 4.0 and Gemini 1.5 Pro. The system delivers accurate, contextually relevant responses from a curated IT knowledge base through an intuitive user interface. The chatbot was designed following a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, involving iterative cycles of design, development, and evaluation. The core technologies employed include Python, the LangChain framework for the RAG pipeline, and a FAISS vector store for efficient semantic search. Performance evaluation was conducted using a test set of 20 questions reviewed by domain experts. The results indicated that GPT-4.0 achieved higher accuracy and precision (average score of 4.60/5), while Gemini 1.5 Pro demonstrated superior response speed (3.28s vs. 4.29s). Overall, the study validates the feasibility of deploying RAG-based architectures in academic IT support environments and highlights valuable insights into optimizing multiple LLMs to balance response quality and speed.

Keywords: *Retrieval-Augmented Generation, Chatbot, Large Language Models, GPT-4, Gemini, Academic Support, Semantic Search*